

ASSESSMENT AND ENHANCEMENT OF THE COURSE DESIGN OF INTERNET AND COMPUTING FUNDAMENTALS PROGRAM IN TUBLAY SCHOOL OF HOME INDUSTRIES

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ABSTRACT

In the Philippines, despite multiple curriculum reforms such as K to 12 and the MATATAG Curriculum, the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) course under the Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program has remained unchanged. This study assessed the course design of ICF Program for Grade 7 students at Tublay School of Home Industries. Specifically, it examined teacher implementers' perceptions of the strengths and weaknesses of the program's course design components—content, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources, methodologies, and assessment methods—along with their coping strategies in the teaching program. The study employed a quantitative descriptive-survey design. The respondents were 33 purposively selected Technical-Vocational Education teachers who had taught or were teaching the ICF Program. Data were collected using a researcher-made survey questionnaire, which underwent content validation by experts and reliability testing, yielding Cronbach's alpha values ranging from 0.79 to 0.86. Descriptive statistics, particularly mean scores, were utilized to analyze the level of agreement on strengths, weaknesses, and coping strategies. Findings revealed that the strengths of the ICF Program are evident in its learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources, methodologies, and assessment methods. However, content was identified as the main weakness due to its outdated, shallow, and poorly organized structure. Teachers coped with these challenges through peer support, technology integration, and reflective classroom strategies, though limited emphasis was placed on research-based improvements. The study's primary output was a redesigned ICF course content aligned with modern digital literacy standards.

Keywords: *ICF course design, ICF course design's strength, ICF course design's weakness, teacher implementers' coping strategies*

INTRODUCTION

Curriculum refers to the organized set of educational plans and outcomes, incorporating teaching materials, methods, and assessments, with the aim of facilitating learners' learning in a structured manner. (Brown, 2016). Similarly, Ornstein and Hunkins (2018) defined the term "curriculum" as the structured set of educational experiences and content offered by schools to meet educational objectives. This includes, but not limited to, planned interactions between teachers, learners, and the material being taught, with the goal of facilitating learning. Hence, a curriculum refers to the overarching framework that outlines what is to be taught in a particular program or course.

In the Department of Education (DepEd), for the 21st century, the institution has already implemented four curricula aiming to address educational concerns to improve the quality and relevance of education. These curricula in order of arrangement include the Basic Education Curriculum (BEC) of 2002, the Secondary Education Curriculum (SEC) of 2010 also known as the Understanding by Design Curriculum, the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum of 2013 also known as the K to 12 Curriculum, and the MATATAG Curriculum of 2024. However, prior the implementation of the BEC 2002, the curriculum in the basic education in the Philippines was primarily characterized by the 1990 curriculum framework (Department of Education, 2002, 2010, 2013, 2024).

Under the umbrella of curriculum is course design. Course design pertains to the systematic planning of a specific course which centers on the learning objectives, instructional strategies, and assessment tools to be used in the teaching process. It involves creating a learning experience tailored to students' needs and may include elements such as content delivery methods, technology integration, and active learning strategies (Baldwin et al., 2018).

To differentiate curriculum from course design, course design answers the question on how the content will be delivered and experienced by learners, involving pedagogical best practices to facilitate teaching and learning process. It centers on the instructional approach while curriculum concentrates on topics, concepts, and skills to be taught within a course. In summary, course design is primarily concerned with the what are the processes in the instructional milieu while course curriculum deals with the content of what is being taught (Anderson & Dron, 2011; McGee & Reis, 2012, Romiszowski, 2016)

Tublay School of Home Industries (TSHI), established in 1971, is one of the public secondary technical-vocational schools in the Schools Division Office (SDO) of Benguet. As one of the oldest public schools established in the Division, TSHI has participated in the implementation of the four basic education curricula in the 21st century: BEC 2002, SEC 2010, K to 12 Curriculum 2013, and MATATAG Curriculum 2024. Besides

implementing DepEd's main given curriculum. TSHI implements related programs mandated by DepEd in relation to TSHI being a technical-vocational high school.

Build from BEC 2002, the Redesigned Technical- Vocational High School Program was implemented in 2005. Highlights in the implementing guidelines of the program that in the Technical-Vocational Education (TVE) in the first-year high school, the four components of TVE shall be offered (Home Economics, Agriculture and Fishery Arts, Industrial Arts, and Entrepreneurship) while in the second year to fourth year, the learners specialize in a specific component. On top, TVE subjects are to be offered on a 120-minute daily time frame (Department of Education, 2005).

The Redesigned Technical-Vocational High School Program was further improved and in 2007, TSHI started to implement the Strengthened Technical Vocational Education Program (STVEP) as one of the listed official 140 technical-vocational school STVEP implementers in the country stipulated in DepEd Order No. 48, s. 2007 (Decentralizing Management of the Strengthened Technical-Vocational Education Program). Being one of the technical-vocational schools implementing STVEP, TSHI offered additional and mandatory subjects in 2009 as mandated by DepEd Order No. 69, s. 2009 (Additional Curriculum Guidelines for the 282 Technical- Vocational Secondary Schools effective S.Y. 2009-2010). One of the required subjects to be taken by students in a STVEP school is Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF). This subject should be taken by the learners from their first year to their third-year high school. (Department Education, 2009). In 2012, in support for the implementation of K to 12 Curriculum of 2013, DepEd provided other guidelines for the implementation of STVEP indicated in DepEd Order No. 67, s. 2012, but the implementation for the course ICF remains the same as this will be taken from Grade 7 (formerly first-year high school) to Grade 9 (formerly third-year high school).

Over the years, a number of studies have focused on technical- vocational education as area of concern. In the Philippines itself, many studies had this as the subject having DepEd as the primary institution involved. The study of Cabahug and Caballero (2015) assessed the optimal readiness of Zamboanga del Sur for the implementation of the K to 12 senior high school technical–vocational livelihood track. Ramos (2021) evaluated the implementation of technical -vocational livelihood track in public senior high schools in the Division of Batangas. Similarly, Ferrer (2022) assessed the status of implementation of technical-vocational-livelihood track in secondary schools in the District of Botolan, Zambales. Likewise, the study of Geraldizo and Dabasol (2022) centered on assessing the senior high school technical-vocational livelihood track in Carcar City, Cebu.

Other researchers include additional variables to understand specific concerns in technical-vocational education. Rusiana and Flores' (2019) study studied the level of availability of equipment and tools for the effective teaching and learning in the senior high school technical- vocational and livelihood track. The research of Espinas et al. (2020) centered on soliciting relevant technical-vocational livelihood education (TVLE) strategies and indicators (S&Is) that can be utilized to develop a contextualized mathematics teaching module. Santos (2021) analyzed the communication requirements

in the technical-vocational-livelihood track while Barerra (2022) explored the availability of instructional material models for the technical-vocational livelihood curriculum implementation for public senior high schools. For Pangan (2022), she delved on the teaching strategies of technical-vocational teachers and student satisfaction; whereas, Olaguer and Pelayo (2023) analyzed the lived experiences in performance assessments of the students in technical-vocational livelihood Senior High School. As for Alarcon et al. (2024), they focused on studying the effectiveness of the technical-vocational-livelihood education in terms of implementation and learning environment.

Many studies were conducted concentrating on technical-vocational education as a program in general. Most of these studies aim to evaluate the implementation of technical-vocational education program under the K to 12 Curriculum (Cabahug & Caballero, 2015; Ferrer, 2022; Geraldizo & Dabasol, 2022; Ramos, 2021). Moreover, since most of the studies focused on the K to 12 curriculum, many of the researches reviewed centered on the technical-vocational livelihood program in the Senior High School (Olaguer & Pelayo 2023; Rusiana and Flores' 2019; Pangan, 2022; Santos, 2021). With these, a gap observed is there is limited account of study which analyze and evaluate a specific course offered by Strengthened Technical Vocational Education Program (STVEP) school specifically in the Junior High School.

In relation, Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) is one of the mandatory courses which is taken by learners for three years in a STVEP school. However, throughout the years, as technology advances, the course design of ICF remains the same. In fact, its course design is not changed nor revised despite the education reform in 2013 known as the Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum Act or the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum and even the recent education reform in 2024 known as the MATATAG Curriculum.

The abovementioned statement including that the researcher is an ICF teacher serves as the motivation of the researcher to conduct a study on assessing the course design of ICF Program. The researcher intends to evaluate the ICF course design for the first-year high school because it is the foundation of the two higher year ICF subjects. The researcher believes that in analyzing the strengths and weaknesses of a particular program, one should start with its foundation, with its basics. For the ICF program, that is its course design for its first-year high school learners. If a program's foundation is strong, it implies that it has the ability to support branching subjects from it.

The researcher believes that the results of study will provide advantages to many education stakeholders. First, in the school level, the TVE teachers particularly teachers teaching ICF are hoped to benefit from the study since the results of the study will provide them detailed data with regard to the evaluated strengths and weaknesses of the course design of ICF for the first-year high school. Also, for the school administrators and TVE department heads in schools implementing STVEP, through the results of the study, they can use the data to either frame an enhancement or intervention program in order to continuously improve the ICF Program implementation. For the Schools Division Office, the results of the study are hoped to provide enough information with reference to ICF

course design which they can use for any professional purpose the information may serve. Furthermore, the study can help other researchers and curriculum developers obtain additional information which they can use for improving ICF course design. Finally, the study is primarily conducted for the learners serving as the main education stakeholder. The study can help in ensuring that the learners take a 21st century program with a 21st century course design for them to eventually contribute in building a 21st century nation.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess the course design of Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) Program particularly for the first-year students in Tublay School of Home Industries. Specifically, it sought answer to the following questions:

1. What is the level of agreement on the strength of the course design component of Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program as perceived by the teacher implementers along:
 - a. content,
 - b. learning outcomes,
 - c. assessment criteria,
 - d. resources needed,
 - e. methodologies, and
 - f. assessment method?
2. What is the level of agreement on the weakness of the course design component of Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program as perceived by the teacher implementers along:
 - a. content,
 - b. learning outcomes,
 - c. assessment criteria,
 - d. resources needed,
 - e. methodologies, and
 - f. assessment method?
3. What is the level of use of the coping strategies of teacher implementers in implementing the Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program?
4. What output can be developed based on the obtained results of the level of agreement on the strengths and weaknesses of Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program?

METHODOLOGY

The study is quantitative descriptive in approach. In quantitative research, the researcher mainly utilizes post-positivist for developing knowledge; that is, the approach rejects that a researcher can be a sole observer of the social world (Creswell, 2013). Specifically, the design is descriptive-survey. Descriptive-survey study is a quantitative research methodology used to unveil in-depth knowledge on a phenomenon. Moreover,

the design helps to fulfill the aim of analyzing the frequencies and identifying patterns in the survey responses.

The respondents of the study were the teachers of Tublay School of Home Industries (TSHI) in Schools Division Office (SDO) of Benguet. Specifically, the respondents were all the TSHI teachers who have taught or teaching the ICF Program. Overall, there were 33 qualified teachers who served as respondents based on the inclusion criteria set. The researcher used purposive sampling. Creswell (2013) described this type of sampling where the respondents possess a similar trait or characteristic. The researcher purposefully samples individuals or sites based on membership in a subgroup that has defining characteristics.

A survey questionnaire served as the primary research tool of the study. The questionnaire has three parts in which each part provided data to answer the study's first three research questions. As the research instrument was researcher-made questionnaire and the tool was not adopted, the tool undergone validity and reliability testing. As for the face and content validity of the instrument, three TVE/TVL Department Heads in three different STVEP schools examined and evaluated its appropriateness, content, and structure. Also, the mechanics of the survey-questionnaire was checked by a Master Teacher whose field of specialization is English in one of the STVEP schools. For its reliability testing, the constructed instrument was administered to the ICF teachers in two STVEP schools. To determine the reliability score of the questionnaire, internal consistency through Cronbach Alpha was utilized.

In the data gathering procedure, a formal letter of request expressing the researcher's intention to conduct the study at TSHI was first submitted to the School Head for approval. Once permission was granted, the researcher proceeded with the data-gathering process. Prior to the distribution of the survey questionnaire, all identified respondents were provided with an Informed Consent Form. The form indicates the objectives of the study, the voluntary nature of participation, the confidentiality measures, and the rights of the respondent. Respondents were informed that they had the right to refuse or withdraw from the study at any point, and that they may request access to their own responses unless restricted by ongoing data analysis or ethical review protocols. Only those who signed the consent form were included in the data collection. The survey questionnaire was administered in person to ensure that participants personally accomplished the instrument and to allow the researcher to clarify procedural concerns without influencing responses. After completion, the answered questionnaires were collected immediately to maintain the integrity and confidentiality of the data. Throughout the process, ethical standards were strictly upheld. All responses were kept confidential, used solely for research purposes, and stored securely to prevent unauthorized access.

Appropriate statistical procedures were applied to generate a detailed numerical interpretation of the respondents' answers, ensuring accuracy and objectivity in the analysis. Descriptive statistics was used to interpret gathered data from the survey questionnaire. For Statement of the Problem (SOP) No. 1, descriptive statistics was employed to treat the collected raw data to determine the level of agreement on the

strength of the course design component of Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program along content, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources needed, methodologies, and assessment method. Specifically, mean was used as the level of agreement on the strength of the course design component is treated as a scale variable. For treating the collected raw data to answer SOP No. 2, descriptive statistics was again used to determine the level of agreement on the weakness of course design component of ICF Program, and mean was again used as level of agreement on the weakness of course design component is treated as a scale variable. With reference to the SOP No. 3, since the goal was to identify the level of use of the coping strategies of teacher implementers in implementing the ICF Program, descriptive statistics specifically mean was again utilized.

The study focused on the evaluation of the course design of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) program for Grade 7 only. It examines the structure, content, and alignment of the Grade 7 ICF course based on established course design criteria. It does not include the evaluation of the ICF course design for Grades 8 and 9. Therefore, the findings cannot be generalized to the entire ICF program across other grade levels.

RESULTS

Level of Agreement on the Strength of ICF’s Course Design Components

Table 1 provides account of the ICF teacher implementers’ level of agreement on the strength of the course design component. Among the course design component evaluated include the content, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources needed, methodologies, and assessment method. As reflected from the table, the results show a mixed evaluation of the course design components of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program as perceived by teacher implementers.

Table 1. Level of agreement on the strength of the course design component of ICF Program as perceived by the teacher implementers

Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program Course Design Component	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETA- TION
A. Content		
1. The contents are current and up-to-date.	1.48	Strongly Disagree
2. The contents are well-organized and easy to follow.	2.36	Disagree
3. The contents are sufficient in depth.	2.39	Disagree
Overall	2.08	Disagree
B. Learning Outcomes		

1. The learning outcomes are relevant to current situation.	3.21	Agree
2. The learning outcomes are well-aligned with the course contents.	2.91	Agree
3. The learning outcomes are measurable and assessable through set assessments methods.	2.97	Agree
Overall	3.03	Agree
C. Assessment Criteria		
1. The assessment criteria are in line with the current applications.	3.00	Agree
2. The assessment criteria are aligned with the learning outcomes of the course.	3.00	Agree
3. The assessment criteria allow theoretical and practical demonstration of knowledge and skills learned.	2.82	Agree
Overall	2.94	Agree
D. Resources Needed		
1. The needed resources indicated in the course design are up-to-date.	3.45	Strongly Agree
2. The needed resources indicated in the course design are readily available in the implementing institution.	3.18	Agree
3. The needed resources indicated in the course design are adequate to achieve the set learning outcomes.	2.85	Agree
Overall	3.16	Agree
E. Methodologies		
1. The methodologies are updated depending on the needs.	3.12	Agree
2. The methodologies are consistent with the course contents and course learning outcomes.	3.12	Agree
3. The methodologies address the different learning styles and needs.	2.94	Agree
Overall	3.06	Agree
F. Assessment Method		
1. The assessment methods are updated depending on the needs.	3.33	Strongly Agree
2. The assessments methods measured both theoretical knowledge and practical skills.	3.09	Agree
3. The assessment methods are aligned well with the course contents, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, and methodologies.	3.09	Agree
Overall	3.17	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 (Strongly Disagree); 1.75-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.24 (Agree); 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

In detail, for content, the numerical results in Table 5 mean that teacher implementers generally disagreed with the strength of the content of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals Program, with an overall mean of 2.08 interpreted as Disagree. Specifically, they strongly disagreed that the contents are current and up-to-date (1.48). The respondents also disagreed on the organization and clarity of the contents (2.36) and on the sufficiency of depth (2.39). These findings highlight that the content aspect of the program needs substantial revision and updating to meet the expectations of implementers and to ensure that learners gain relevant and adequate knowledge.

In contrast to content, the learning outcomes were viewed more positively, with an overall mean of 3.03 interpreted as Agree. The teacher implementers agreed that the outcomes are relevant to the current situation (3.21) and are measurable through assessments (2.97). They also agreed that learning outcomes are well-aligned with course contents (2.91). This indicates that while the contents may be outdated, the intended learning goals remain meaningful, aligned, and achievable.

For the assessment criteria, these were rated positively with an overall mean of 2.94 (Agree). Teacher implementers agreed that the criteria are aligned with learning outcomes (3.00) and reflect current applications (3.00). They also agreed, though with a slightly lower mean (2.82), that the criteria allow both theoretical and practical demonstration of knowledge and skills.

As regards resources, the course design component was rated favorably, with an overall mean of 3.16 (Agree). The strongest point was the perception that resources indicated in the course are up-to-date (3.45). Teacher implementers also agreed that resources are readily available (3.18) and adequate to achieve outcomes (2.85). Although generally positive, the slightly lower score on adequacy suggests that while resources are accessible, they may still be insufficient in quantity or scope for fully supporting the program goals.

With reference to methodologies as a course design component, the teacher implementers agreed with the strength of methodologies used, reflected in the overall mean of 3.06 (Agree). They indicated agreement that the methodologies are updated based on needs (3.12) and consistent with course contents and learning outcomes (3.12). They also agreed that the methodologies address different learning styles (2.94). These findings suggest that instructional strategies are still considered relevant and flexible.

Finally, for assessments methods, this course design component received the highest overall agreement (3.17), with teacher implementers strongly agreeing that they are updated depending on needs (3.33). They also agreed that the methods measure both theoretical knowledge and practical skills (3.09) and are aligned with contents, outcomes, criteria, and methodologies (3.09). This reflects a strong confidence in the program's assessment practices.

Level of Agreement on the Weakness of ICF's Course Design Components

Table 2 accounts the numerical findings on the level of agreement of teacher implementers on the perceived weaknesses of the course design components of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) Program. The six major areas of course design namely content, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources needed, methodologies, and assessment methods are again covered. Overall, the teacher-respondents' answers were able to indicate which aspects of the course design are considered weak and which remain strong.

Table 2. Level of agreement on the weakness of the course design component of ICF Program as perceived by the teacher implementers

INTERNET AND COMPUTING FUNDAMENTALS PROGRAM COURSE DESIGN COMPONENT	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
A. Content		
1. The contents are outdated.	3.39	Strongly Agree
2. The contents are poorly organized and difficult to follow.	2.61	Agree
3. The contents lack sufficient depth.	2.58	Agree
Overall	2.85	Agree
B. Learning Outcomes		
1. The learning outcomes are irrelevant to the current situation.	1.82	Disagree
2. The learning outcomes are poorly aligned with the course contents.	2.12	Disagree
3. The learning outcomes are immeasurable through set assessment methods.	2.03	Disagree
Overall	1.99	Disagree
C. Assessment Criteria		
1. The assessment criteria are out of line with the current applications.	2.03	Disagree
2. The assessment criteria diverge from the learning outcomes of the course.	2.00	Disagree
3. The assessment criteria fail to show theoretical and practical demonstration of knowledge and skills learned.	2.12	Disagree
Overall	2.05	Disagree
D. Resources Needed		
1. The needed resources indicated in the course design are outdated.	1.64	Strongly Disagree
2. The needed resources indicated in the course design are unavailable in the implementing institution.	1.76	Disagree

3. The needed resources indicated in the course design are inadequate to achieve the set learning outcomes.	1.97	Disagree
Overall	1.79	Disagree
E. Methodologies		
1. The methodologies remain unchanged despite the needs.	1.82	Disagree
2. The methodologies are inconsistent with the course contents and course learning outcomes.	1.82	Disagree
3. The methodologies fail to accommodate different learning styles and needs.	1.91	Disagree
Overall	1.85	Disagree
F. Assessment Method		
1. The assessment methods remain unchanged despite the needs.	1.64	Strongly Disagree
2. The assessment methods fail to measure theoretical knowledge or practical skills.	1.79	Disagree
3. The assessment methods are misaligned with the course contents, learning outcomes, assessment criteria, and methodologies.	1.82	Disagree
Overall	1.75	Disagree

Legend: 1.00-1.74 (Strongly Disagree); 1.75-2.49 (Disagree); 2.50-3.24 (Agree); 3.25-4.00 (Strongly Agree)

To begin, for the content, the teacher implementers generally agreed that the content of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) Program has notable weaknesses. With an overall mean of 2.85 interpreted as agree, the strongest concern revealed was that the teacher implementers regarded the ICF course design contents as outdated, with a mean of 3.39 (strongly agree). The respondents further agreed that the materials are poorly organized (2.61) and lacks sufficient depth (2.58). These findings point to a pressing need to update and enrich the content to ensure it is current, logically structured, and comprehensive enough to support effective learning in a rapidly evolving technological landscape.

In contrast, the learning outcomes, as an aspect of the course design, received an overall mean of 1.99, which corresponds to disagree. Teachers disagreed that the outcomes are irrelevant (1.82), misaligned with the course content (2.12), or immeasurable using the set assessment methods (2.03). This indicates that the outcomes are generally regarded as valid, relevant, and measurable, signifying that this component does not present significant weaknesses but rather demonstrates alignment with instructional goals.

Similarly, the assessment criteria showed no indication of major weakness, with an overall mean of 2.05 (disagree). The respondents disagreed that the criteria are inconsistent with current applications (2.03), diverge from the course learning outcomes (2.00), or fail to demonstrate both theoretical and practical learning (2.12). Overall, the

respondents, consider the assessment criteria as appropriate and supportive of both knowledge-based and performance-based evaluation.

In terms of resources, the overall mean of 1.79 (disagree) indicates that teacher implementers did not identify this as an area of weakness of the ICF course design. The respondents strongly disagreed that the indicated resources are outdated (1.64) and also disagreed with the claim that resources are unavailable (1.76) or inadequate to meet learning outcomes (1.97). This implies that the resources enumerated in the ICF course design are sufficient, accessible, and relevant to program implementation.

Also, the methodologies as a component of the ICF course design received an overall mean of 1.85 (disagree), reflecting that the teacher implementers did not view instructional strategies as problematic. They disagreed with the idea that methodologies remain static (1.82), are inconsistent with the content and outcomes (1.82), or fail to accommodate diverse learning needs (1.91). This then highlights the adaptability and pedagogical appropriateness of the teaching strategies applied within the program.

Lastly, the assessment method obtained an overall mean of 1.75, also interpreted as disagree. The teacher implementers strongly disagreed that assessment methods remain unchanged (1.64) and further disagreed that they fail to capture theoretical or practical skills (1.79) or are misaligned with other course components (1.82). This demonstrates that the assessment method is considered current, aligned, and effective in measuring intended learning outcomes.

Level of Use of the Coping Strategies of Teacher Implementers in Implementing the ICF Program

Table 3 indicates the level of use of coping strategies employed by teacher implementers in carrying out the ICF Program. The data show how teachers adapt to the challenges of implementation through varied approaches such as seeking guidance from peers, utilizing technological resources, and reflecting on teaching practices. The results reveal a combination of strategies that range from "Never Used" to "Always Used," with an overall mean of 3.00, qualitatively interpreted as "Often Used." This indicates that while certain strategies are consistently practiced, others are employed less frequently, reflecting the diverse ways teachers manage the demands of the program.

Table 3. Level of use of the coping strategies of teacher implementers in implementing the ICF Program

COPING STRATEGIES OF TEACHER IMPLEMENTERS IN IMPLEMENTING THE INTERNET AND COMPUTING FUNDAMENTALS PROGRAM	MEAN	QUALITATIVE INTERPRETATION
1. I seek guidance from experienced ICF teachers.	3.82	Always Used

2. I communicate with parents to support their child's learning.	2.12	Sometimes Used
3. I attend professional development workshops related to ICF.	2.33	Sometimes Used
4. I utilize online resources to improve my skills in teaching ICF.	3.58	Always Used
5. I conduct research study to improve my teaching practice.	1.73	Never Used
6. I develop contextualized materials to address my learners' needs.	3.39	Often Used
7. I regularly reflect on my teaching practices to determine classroom problems and solutions.	3.15	Often Used
8. I use graphic organizers to help structure information.	2.79	Often Used
9. I keep up-to-date with the latest technological trends and tools.	3.58	Always Used
10. I create a classroom technology policy to ensure proper use of equipment.	2.97	Often Used
11. I develop checklists for me to easily track my learners' progress.	3.09	Often Used
12. I create a reward system to acknowledge learners' achievements and to encourage learners' active participation.	2.88	Often Used
13. I experiment with different teaching styles to find what works best.	3.24	Often Used
14. I use feedback from learners to refine my teaching methods.	3.09	Often Used
15. I develop a system for collecting, organizing, and evaluating learners' work.	3.24	Often Used
Overall	3.0	Often Used

Legend: 1.00-1.74 (Never Used); 1.75-2.49 (Sometimes Used); 2.50-3.24 (Often Used); 3.25-4.00 (Always Used)

In a more elaborate manner, among the strategies, seeking guidance from experienced ICF teachers with a mean of 3.82, utilizing online resources to improve teaching skills with a mean of 3.58, and keeping up-to-date with technological trends and tools also with a mean of 3.58 were rated as "Always Used." This suggests that teachers strongly rely on collegial support and technology-driven resources to address instructional challenges.

In contrast, strategies such as developing contextualized materials with a mean of 3.39, reflecting on teaching practices with a mean of 3.15, experimenting with teaching styles with a mean of 3.24, and using learner feedback with a mean of 3.09 were classified as "Often Used." This reflects a moderate but consistent effort of teachers to personalize instruction, engage in reflective practice, and improve classroom delivery based on

learner needs. Similarly, practical classroom strategies like creating checklists with a mean of 3.09, reward systems with a mean of 2.88, and graphic organizers with a mean of 2.79 were also applied often, suggesting their usefulness in classroom management and learner engagement, though not as heavily emphasized as technology-based strategies.

On the other hand, strategies such as communicating with parents with a mean of 2.12 and attending professional development workshops with a mean of 2.33 were only “Sometimes Used.” This indicates a weaker engagement in parent collaboration and external training, which may be due to limited opportunities, time constraints, or lack of institutional support. The least utilized coping mechanism was conducting research studies to improve teaching practice with a mean of 1.73, which was interpreted as “Never Used.” This highlights a gap in research-based coping strategies, suggesting that while teachers value practical and readily applicable methods, they rarely turn to formal research as a means of coping.

Output Constructed Based on the Obtained Results of the Level of Agreement on the Strengths and Weaknesses of ICF Course Design

As revealed in the study, the major weakness of the ICF Program for Grade 7 lies in its course design content, which was perceived by teacher implementers as outdated, lacking sufficient depth, and poorly organized. This indicates that the existing ICF course design does not fully meet the present demands of learners nor the evolving requirements of technological education. Thus, the output of this study points to the urgent need to redesign the course design content of the ICF Program to ensure that it is current, comprehensive, and systematically structured to support effective teaching and learning.

The primary output of the study is the redesign of ICF course design content for Grade 7. The revised ICF course design aims to address the identified weakness in outdated, shallow, and poorly organized content by restructuring the curriculum into clearly defined content aligned with modern digital literacy standards.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of the Numerical Findings on Teacher Implementers’ Level of Agreement on the Strength of ICF’s Course Design Components

Based on the numerical results, it can be concluded that the strengths of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) Program’s course design are evident in its learning outcomes, its assessment criteria, the adequacy of its resources, its methodologies, and its assessment methods.

First, the teacher implementers perceived that the learning outcomes indicated in the ICF course design are relevant, well-aligned with the course contents, and measurable making the course design component supportive to effective teaching and

learning. This means that the learning outcomes of the course design of ICF Program are still viewed by the respondents positively. Krathwohl (2002) and Harden (2002) agreed that learning outcomes are regarded as relevant when these connect classroom instruction with real-world applications to make learning more engaging and purposeful. Biggs and Tang (2011), on the other hand, noted that learning outcomes are considered well-aligned with the course contents if these establish clear connection between what is taught and what is expected of learners. Finally, for measurable learning outcomes, Kirkwood and Price (2014) defined these as learning outcomes evaluating not only theoretical understanding but also the practical skills essential for workforce readiness.

Likewise, the teacher implementers generally hold a positive perception of the assessment criteria in the ICF course design. As the highest ratings were given to the criteria's alignment with learning outcomes and reflection of current applications, this suggests that assessments are both pedagogically coherent and responsive to technological developments. According to Brown and Glasner (2003), well-aligned assessment ensures that students are evaluated on what they are expected to learn, thereby reinforcing both instructional clarity and learning efficiency. Similarly, Knight (2002) emphasized that assessments reflecting real-world contexts make learning more meaningful and improve student engagement. On the other hand, although the mean rating for the statement that the assessment criteria allow both theoretical and practical demonstration of knowledge and skills is slightly lower than the other indicators under assessment criteria, it still falls within the agree range, suggesting that teacher implementers recognize the presence of opportunities for applied learning in the ICF course design. Brown and Glasner (2003) and Sambell et al. (2013) emphasized that the inclusion of performance-based assessment criteria strengthens students' preparation for professional demands. This performance-based assessment criteria are perceived to be observed by the teacher implementers in the ICF course design making them agree that the assessment criteria ensure that the learners develop not only cognitive understanding but also essential problem-solving and technical implementation skills.

For assessment of the resources component of the ICF course design, the result yielded an overall favorable rating which indicates that the teacher implementers generally perceive the resource provisions of the program as supportive of learning. The results can be attributed to the teacher implementers perception that the availability of adequate and relevant resources is significant because it enables them to effectively deliver instruction and ensures that learning outcomes are met. Adeoye et al. (2020) averred that adequate resources—whether technological, instructional, or infrastructural—enhance students' engagement, foster innovative teaching practices, and support alignment between course design and implementation. The claim is supported by Adarkwah (2021) reiterating that without sufficient resources, even well-designed courses may fail to achieve their intended outcomes, highlighting the crucial role of resource provision in sustaining educational quality.

With reference to methodologies as a course design component, teacher implementers viewed the approaches used as generally relevant and supportive of teaching and learning. They recognized that the instructional strategies were aligned with

course contents and intended learning outcomes, indicating coherence between curriculum design and delivery. The methodologies were also viewed as responsive to learners' needs, reflecting a degree of adaptability. However, while there was recognition that different learning styles are addressed, the statement on methodologies addressing the different learning styles and needs having the lowest mean among the three indicators may stressed attention on inclusive and flexible strategies to accommodate diverse learners, particularly in heterogeneous classrooms. Research underscores that learner-centered and adaptive methodologies not only enhance student engagement but also improve knowledge retention and critical thinking skills (Prince, 2004; Tomlinson, 2014). Moreover, inclusive teaching strategies ensure equitable learning opportunities, especially in contexts where students vary widely in ability, background, and learning preferences (Florian & Black-Hawkins, 2011).

Last, for assessment methods, the findings imply that teacher implementers show confidence that the assessment methods are able to evaluate both knowledge and skills while remaining aligned with instructional goals. They believe that the assessment methods ensure that that teaching and learning are not only measured but also guided toward desired outcomes. According to Black and Wiliam (1998), when assessments methods are well-aligned with curriculum objectives, these provide constructive feedback that helps students improve and encourages deeper engagement with learning. Furthermore, diverse and authentic assessment methods enhance students' capacity to apply knowledge in real-world contexts, supporting both academic achievement and skill development (Gulikers et al., 2004). Research also highlights that adaptive assessment methods improve inclusivity by addressing the varying needs of learners and ensuring fairness in evaluation (Brookhart, 2013). These perspectives suggest that the program's assessment methods are reliable and capable of promoting meaningful learning outcomes.

Overall, ICF Program demonstrates overall strength in most of its course design components. While the content as of component of ICF Program's course design may require further enhancement, the findings suggest that the teacher implementers perceive that the course design is still fundamentally strong and capable of supporting effective teaching and meaningful student learning.

Analysis of the Numerical Findings on the Teacher Implementers' Level of Agreement on the Weakness of ICF's Course Design Components

The findings suggest that the only course design component where weaknesses were strongly recognized is the content, particularly with issues of being outdated, poorly organized, and lacking depth. In contrast, all other components—learning outcomes, assessment criteria, resources, methodologies, and assessment methods—were not perceived as weaknesses, as teacher implementers consistently disagreed with negative statements regarding their effectiveness. This underscores the need for targeted curriculum enhancement in content while maintaining the strengths of other course design components.

The result can be attributed to the fact that since the implementation of the Internet and Computing Fundamentals (ICF) Program in STVEP schools in S.Y. 2009-2010, the content component of ICF Program's course design has remained unrevised, which may lead to persistent weaknesses in its delivery. Teacher implementers perceived that the contents are outdated, poorly organized, and lacking sufficient depth, suggesting that the curriculum has not kept pace with the evolving demands of the field. The absence of revisions highlights a gap in ensuring curricular relevance and responsiveness, making the content less effective in supporting both instructional goals and learner needs. Thus, this underscores the importance of updating the ICF content to align with current technological advancements and educational standards.

Regular curriculum review and revision are essential to ensure that educational programs remain relevant to both industry demands and learner needs. Studies emphasize that outdated content can hinder the development of 21st-century skills, particularly in technology-related fields where knowledge and practices rapidly evolve (Voogt & Roblin, 2012). Without timely updates, course materials risk misalignment with current standards and practices, which may compromise learners' readiness for further education or employment (Cai, 2013; Ornstein & Hunkins, 2018; Reddy, 2019). Moreover, research highlights that curriculum responsiveness—defined as the ability to adapt content to changing societal and technological contexts—is a critical factor in maintaining quality education (Fullan & Langworthy 2014). Therefore, the lack of revisions in the ICF Program content since its implementation more than a decade ago represents a significant gap, reinforcing the urgency of systematic curriculum renewal to ensure both instructional relevance and student competency development.

Analysis of the Numerical Findings of the Teacher Implementers' Coping Strategies in Implementing the ICF Program

The findings suggest that ICF teacher implementers cope with program challenges primarily through peer support, technology integration, and reflective classroom strategies, while less emphasis is placed on parent engagement, professional development, and research-based practices. The overall interpretation of "Often Used" underscores that teachers consistently employ coping mechanisms. However, the numerical results on also shows that some areas still need more support especially in conducting research study to improve one's teaching practice.

The findings can be attributed to different factors. According to Bernardo and Mendoza (2020) and Garcia (2019), despite DepEd's mandate encouraging teacher-led research, many public school teachers remain hesitant to engage in formal research activities many teachers lack sufficient trainings in research methodologies, statistical analysis, and academic writing. Another significant factor considered is lack of time. This factor remains to be a constraint in conducting action research for teachers (Kutlay, 2012; Morales, 2016). The mandate of the Civil Service Commission is an eight-hour rendition of services in the school, six (6) hours of which is to be spent for actual classroom teaching while the remaining two (2) hours will be for other activities, which could either be spent inside or outside the school premises. Teachers have a heavy workload that

includes many papers works to accomplish every day, which they work on during their vacant periods falling under the two-hour allotment for curricular tasks (Lapus, 2009). However, there are also teachers who simply lack interest in conducting research studies, these teachers may viewed conducting research as not their duty as classroom teachers. Therefore, these teachers neither do research neither use research in their own classroom (Gomez & Catan, 2021; Ulla et al., 2017).

Despite having various factors why teachers do not engage themselves in conducting research, research studies are essential to enhance teaching practices as it allows teachers to identify effective strategies grounded in evidence rather than relying solely on coping mechanisms (Cochran-Smith & Lytle, 2009). Engaging teachers in practitioner research also empowers them to critically reflect on their practices and make data-driven improvements (Borg, 2010). Furthermore, research participation enhances professional growth, helping educators shift from reactive coping to proactive pedagogical innovation (Zeichner, 2003). Professional development and research also ensure that teachers are not only coping but continuously improving their instructional approaches (Darling-Hammond et al., 2017). Finally, developing a culture of inquiry within schools fosters sustainability of best practices and aligns classroom strategies with broader educational reforms (Burns, 2016). Ultimately, fostering a culture where teachers actively engage in research not only strengthens individual professional practice but also drives continuous improvement in the education system, ensuring that instructional strategies remain relevant, evidence-based, and responsive to evolving classroom challenges.

Bases and Evaluation of the Redesigned ICF Program Course Design Content

In redesigning the content of the course design of Grade 7 ICF Program, several references were considered. Since there is no framed Curriculum Guide specifically for ICF under DepEd's MATATAG Curriculum of 2023, the primary basis of the redesigned ICF Program course design content is the Curriculum Guide of Information and Technology (ICT) for Grade 7 under the MATATAG Curriculum. Since, ICT is offered in regular national high schools and ICF Program should be more advanced in content as it is offered in a secondary school under STVEP, the researcher considered as well several topics in Grade 8 ICT to be included in the redesigned content of Grade 7 ICF (Department of Education, 2023).

Also, the Understanding by Design guide by Wiggins and McTighe (2012) directed the researcher in framing the course design content. Another relevant paper which guided the researcher was the paper of Tomson (2019) on the spiral progression approach in the K to 12 Curriculum. Both references have been also used in the framing of the Curriculum Guides of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) for Grades 6 to 10 in the MATATAG Curriculum.

Other references in redesigning the course design content include the UNESCO ICT competency framework for teachers Implementation guide (UNESCO, 2018), United Nations Children's Fund's ICT for learning process and tools (UNICEF, 2018), Lim et al. (2010) and Herring et al. (2016) ICT toolkit for teacher education institutions, and Flor's

(2008) framework on ICT for basic education in the Philippines. In addition, Ellis' (2022) concept of task-based learning was also regarded by the researcher having the believe that effective learning takes place when learners engage in meaningful tasks rather than memorize contents in isolation.

After the revision of the ICF course design content, the proposed ICF course design content was subjected to an essential process of validation. Validation is crucial because the ICF program is a specialized curriculum intended for STVEP schools, and its redesign involved synthesizing content from different official guides (Grade 7 and Grade 8 ICT) and external pedagogical frameworks. Therefore, evaluation was necessary to confirm the course's curricular validity, ensuring the integrated content was appropriate for Grade 7 STVEP students. Also, this is to verify the contents' alignment with current and up-to-date industry practices and to confirm its pedagogical soundness. Three experts in the field validated the proposed output to determine its level of acceptability.

The evaluation focused on three critical course design content components. All three components received a median score of 3, resulting in a qualitative equivalent of "Acceptable". Overall, the redesigned course design reflects a deliberate effort to modernize content, improve organization, and provide greater depth. It aligns competencies with practical applications, fosters responsible use of technology, and equips learners with the digital skills necessary for academic and real-world tasks.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The strengths identified in the Grade 7 ICF Program—namely the learning outcomes, assessment criteria, learning resources, teaching methodologies, and assessment methods—demonstrate that the course is still founded on a sound instructional design.
2. The content of the Grade 7 ICF Program—emerges as the primary area of weakness. Addressing this issue is crucial to updating and improving the course, ensuring it remains relevant, comprehensive, and effective for students' learning.
3. The ICF teacher implementers cope with program challenges primarily through peer support, technology integration, and reflective classroom strategies while no emphasis is placed on conducting research study to improve one's teaching practice.
4. The primary output of the study is the redesign of ICF course design content for Grade 7. The revised ICF course design aims to address the identified weakness in outdated, shallow, and poorly organized content by restructuring the curriculum into clearly defined content aligned with modern digital literacy standards

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions of the study, the following are recommended:

1. Learners should be included in the evaluation of the framed enhanced ICF course design. The school may let the ICF learners evaluate the course design; however,

the researcher-made questionnaire should be contextualized anchored according to the students' level of comprehension.

2. The school may conduct a quarterly review and validation workshop involving the Grade 7 ICF teacher implementers to sustain and enhance the strong components of the ICF Program course design. Regular teacher feedback, alignment with industry standards, and integration of updated teaching methodologies will ensure that the strengths of the program's course design are maintained and further improved.

3. The school may consider prioritizing regular curriculum updates and content review cycles to ensure program content's relevance and depth. The school may form a course review committee that includes teachers, ICT professionals, and curriculum experts to validate and contextualized program's content ensuring that content remains aligned with current technological developments and educational needs.

4. The school needs to provide training and institutional support to encourage teachers to conduct classroom-based research. Professional development programs, research mentoring, and collaboration with academic institutions should be introduced to build teachers' research capability and integrate findings into classroom practices for continuous instructional improvement.

5. The school, with the permission from the District and Division Office, is encouraged to implement the revised ICF course design for Grade 7 for pilot testing to gather feedback from both ICF teachers and learners. Based on evaluation results, the school may conduct further refinements before full-scale adoption.

6. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct similar evaluations of the ICF program course design for Grades 8 and 9 as the scope of this research is limited to assessing only the course design of ICF program course design for Grade 7.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author hereby declares that this study was conducted in full compliance with established ethical standards in research. Informed consent was duly obtained from all respondents prior to their involvement in the study, and they were clearly informed of the purpose, procedures, and voluntary nature of their participation. Participants were assured of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty or consequence. Anonymity and confidentiality of respondents were strictly maintained, with no personal identifying information collected or disclosed, and all data were handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act and relevant institutional guidelines. The well-being of the respondents was safeguarded throughout the research process, as the study involved no invasive procedures, risks, or harm beyond minimal time commitment.

Furthermore, the author affirms that no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of this study, and that the research was undertaken solely for academic and scholarly purposes. Plagiarism was strictly avoided through proper citation and original analysis, and no form of bias was allowed to influence the collection, interpretation, or presentation of the findings. The results of the study were used purely for research, academic dissemination, and program improvement. The authors also disclose that artificial intelligence tools were utilized solely to assist in language refinement and academic writing support, without compromising the integrity, originality, or ownership of the

research content. All interpretations, conclusions, and final outputs remain the responsibility of the authors.

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